

INFLUENCE OF THE TEMPERATURE ON THE CONSOLIDATION AND DIAPHRAGM FORMING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

by Harald E.N. Bersee

Structures & Materials Laboratory
Faculty of Aerospace Engineering
Delft University of Technology

ABSTRACT

It is necessary to develop a good understanding of the processing of thermoplastic composites. A good knowledge of the processing of thermoplastic composites may increase the use of these materials in aircraft structures. With the processing of thermoplastic composites three parameters dominant are pressure, temperature and time. The investigation of the influence of these parameters on the tensile and inplane shear strength and on the diaphragm formability of a thermoplastic composite is described in this paper. The optimum processing temperature from mechanical and diaphragm forming point of view is determined.

Keywords: thermoplastic composites; diaphragm forming; tensile strength; inplane shear strength; processing temperature

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites have several advantages over both thermoset matrix composites and metals, like the potential of low cost manufacturing, high toughness, which makes them very interesting for the use in aircraft structures. It is, therefore, surprising that despite the advantages, like high speed manufacturing, there is still a reserved use of these materials in commercial manufacturing industries in general and in aerospace industries in particular. The reason for this reserved use is the lack of knowledge of the processing of these materials. It is therefore necessary to develop a good understanding of the processing science so that the combinations of high speed manufacturing and high material properties will be realized for the particular composite parts to be made. In this paper, the investigation of consolidation and diaphragm forming of thermoplastic composites will be described.

One of the projects on thermoplastic composites at the Delft University of Technology, is "modelling of consolidation and diaphragm forming of thermoplastic composites". Diaphragm forming is a thermoforming process which is derived from vacuum forming of thermoplastic sheets. In diaphragm forming the laminate is placed between two diaphragms {fig.1}. The diaphragms are clamped onto the mould after

which vacuum is applied between the diaphragms. The mould is then placed into an autoclave and heated to the processing temperature. After reaching the processing time, an hydrostatic pressure will be created which forces the laminate into the mould. The laminate is not clamped and is allowed to slide within the diaphragms. This sliding action creates tensile stresses in the sheet from interfacial shear stresses that reduces wrinkling [ref.1]. The diaphragms have therefore the function of a continuous blankholder. Diaphragm forming gives products with an excellent quality. The cycle times are, however, longer than the cycle times for matched die forming, which is another thermoforming process suitable for thermoplastic composites.

2. CONSOLIDATION AND DIAPHRAGM FORMING EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Goal of the investigation

When thermoplastic composites are being processed, individual plies consolidate into a laminate by bonding at the interfaces. The three most important processing parameters, for both consolidation and diaphragm forming, are pressure (p), temperature (T) and time (t). In order to investigate the influence of one of these parameters, the other two parameters have to be kept constant. In this paper only the influence of the processing temperature, for a constant processing pressure and processing time, will be described. The goal of the investigation was to determine the optimum processing temperature for respectively, consolidation and diaphragm forming.

Figure 1: Diaphragm forming.

2.2 Consolidation experiments

A well consolidated laminate will have improved mechanical properties compared with a poor consolidated laminate especially the matrix dominated properties. Poor consolidation will result in large areas of the interfaces of the plies which do not coalesce and thus results in a large number of micro voids. The bond in the areas of the interfaces, which coalesce is, however, very weak. So the mechanical properties of a laminate are a direct indication of the degree of consolidation of a laminate.

Important mechanical properties are tensile strength, compressive strength, inplane shear strength and interlaminar strength. The influence of the processing temperature on all four mechanical properties was investigated but only the results of the tensile and inplane shear tests were available at the time of writing.

The tensile properties of the laminates were determined according to ASTM D 3039-76. The geometry of the specimens is shown in figure 2. The same test was used for the determination of the inplane shear properties but with the fibres in the $\pm 45^\circ$ direction. The laminates consisted of 6 layers of CETEX.

CETEX is a prepreg made by Ten Cate Holland consisting of PolyEtherImide reinforced with a carbon- or glass fabric.

For the consolidation tests, the reinforcement was a 8H satin E-glass fabric and the fibre volume fraction was 55%. The laminates were consolidated in a hot platen press at varying processing temperatures and with a constant processing pressure and a constant processing time. Care has to be taken with the choice of the constant pressure and time. If the pressure and time are chosen too high, the consolidation of the specimens will be very good even at lower temperatures. This means that the influence of the temperature on the degree of consolidation can not be visualised.

Figure 3: Autoclave used for diaphragm forming.

When the pressure and time are too small, the consolidation of the specimens made at lower temperatures will be very poor. This poor consolidation will result in failure of the specimens before testing. Preliminary tests have shown that laminates consolidated at 300 °C, 5 bar and 5 min have a reasonable degree of consolidation. The pressure was, therefore, taken at 5 bar and the processing time at 5 min. Per processing condition two laminates are produced, one for the tensile tests and one for the inplane shear tests. The laminates have good and bad consolidated spots which are randomly divided through the laminate. There are, therefore, six tensile/inplane shear specimens cut from one laminate. The average value of the six specimens will give a good indication of the degree of consolidation of the laminate. The expectation is that the tensile- and inplane shear strength increases with increasing processing temperature until a certain temperature after which it remains constant.

2.3 Diaphragm forming experiments

The autoclave of the Structures & Materials Laboratory was used for the diaphragm forming experiments. The autoclave {fig.3} has an internal diameter of 1.20 m and an internal length of 1.7 m. It can operate at pressures up to 20 bar and at temperatures up to 400 °C and uses air. The mould consisted of an aluminium inner mould and a

Figure 2: Geometry of the specimens.

steel outer mould {fig.4}. This division into an outer and inner mould, was done in order to be able to quickly change the product form at low costs. The product was a hemisphere with a radius of 70 mm. A hemisphere was chosen for two reasons, namely:

- A hemisphere is rotation symmetric, which makes calculations, like FEM, easier and makes the process independent of the position of the laminate.
- A hemisphere is a product in which all the deformation modes of fibre reinforced plastics occur. These deformation modes are [ref.2, 3]:
 - 1) Interply slip
 - 2) Shear
 - 3) Shear slip
 - 4) Fibre stretching
 - 5) Fibre straightening

Figure 4: Diaphragm forming mould.

8 H-satin E-glass- and 5 H satin carbon fabric reinforced PEI prepreg of Ten Cate and Upilex-R diaphragms of ICI were used for the diaphragm forming of hemispheres. DMTA analyses were made for the determination of the glass transition temperature of PEI (Ultem) and PI (Upilex-R), respectively 215 °C and 265 °C {fig.5 and 6}. The

Figure 5: DMTA analysis of PEI.

viscosity of the matrix has to be low because of the influence on the fabric deformation. The influence of the matrix may be twofold [ref.2]. Firstly, the viscous matrix acts as a lubricant and decreases the internal friction during the motion of fibre bundles in a laminate. Thermoforming will be facilitated in this way and lower forming forces on the laminate are possible. Secondly, the high viscosity of thermoplastic matrices can lead to restrictions of the motion of fibre bundles in a laminate. Visco elastic effects can occur when fabric deformations take place too quickly. The processing temperature has, therefore, to

be well above the Tg of the matrix. The processing temperature has also to be well above the Tg of the diaphragms in order to obtain high elongations. On the other hand the viscosity of the foil has to be high in order to avoid fibre wrinkling. The maximum processing temperature of the Upilex-R diaphragms is 400 °C since Upilex degrades very quickly at temperatures above 400 °C. The processing temperature of

Figure 6: DMTA analysis of Upilex-R.

pressure is created which presses the laminate into the mould. After forming, the product is consolidated for a certain time after which the product will be cooled down under pressure to room temperature. The pressure and consolidation time are the same as for the consolidation tests. Preliminary tests have shown that a pressure of 5 bar is sufficient to deform the laminate.

3. RESULTS CONSOLIDATION TESTS

The results of the tensile and inplane shear tests are given in figure 8 and 9. Every data in the graphs is the average value of the six specimens. The tensile strength

Figure 8: Tensile strength versus processing temperature.

the first test was, therefore, 400 °C. The processing cycle of this test is given in fig.7. After the autoclave has reached the processing temperature, there is a certain dwell time necessary to allow the mould to reach the processing temperature. The mould has no heating elements, which resulted in a considerable dwell time. The pressure is applied from the beginning in order to decrease the heating time. When the mould is at the processing temperature, forming starts by opening the air vents of the mould. The mould is now in contact with the atmosphere outside the autoclave. In this way a hydrostatic

Figure 7: Processing cycle of diaphragm forming.

increases, as expected, with increasing processing temperature. There is, however, a small drop in tensile strength above 245 °C. The drop is probably caused by scatter. Although the six specimens give a good average of the laminate quality, there is only one laminate per condition so additional tests are necessary to verify this conclusion. Above 300 °C, the tensile strength is independent of the processing temperature.

The shear strength versus the processing temperature gives the same dependency of the strength with

the temperature as for the tensile strength. First the shear strength increases with increasing processing temperature until 300 °C. At processing temperatures higher than 300 °C, the shear strength remains constant. Both the dependency of the tensile strength as the shear strength with the processing temperature is according to the expectations. The processing temperature of Glass/PEI should be ≥ 300 °C in order to achieve the highest tensile/inplane shear strength.

Figure 9: Inplane shear strength versus processing temperature.

4. RESULTS DIAPHRAGM FORMING TESTS

The hemispheres made at 400 °C showed three phenomena namely: dry areas {fig.10}, Upilex-wrinkling {fig.11} and fibre wrinkling {fig.12}. The dry areas at the outer surface are caused by stripping of the matrix at the edge of the mould. The viscosity of the matrix at 400 °C, is probably too low.

Figure 10: Stripping of the matrix.

The viscosity of the matrix is increased by decreasing the processing temperature. The hemispheres made at temperatures lower than 370 °C showed no dry areas.

The Upilex wrinkles are in circumferential direction at the edge of the hemisphere. The diaphragms can not slide into the mould but is pinned at the edge of the mould, which results in stripping of the diaphragm. The viscosity of the diaphragms at 400 °C is probably too low to allow the

diaphragm to slide over the edge of the mould. The viscosity of the diaphragms can be increased by decreasing the processing temperature. The amount of Upilex wrinkling gradually decreased with decreasing temperature. The hemispheres formed at 300 °C showed no Upilex wrinkling at all. Fibre wrinkling can be caused by two things:

Figure 11: Upilex wrinkling.

Figure 12: Fibre wrinkling.

{fig.13}. The cause of the fibre wrinkling will therefore be the low stiffness of the diaphragms. Decreasing the processing temperature will increase the stiffness of the diaphragms. The number of fibre wrinkles and the size of the fibre wrinkles decreased gradually with decreasing temperature. Hemispheres formed at 300-320 °C were free of fibre wrinkles {fig.14}. Lowering the processing temperature below 300 °C resulted in diaphragm failure.

From all the diaphragm forming tests it can be concluded that the optimum processing temperature for Glass/PEI should be 300-320 °C.

Figure 14: Hemisphere formed at 300 °C.

- 1) The product shape is very complex and requires shear angles of the fabric of less than 30°. When shear angles of less than 30° are required the fibres will wrinkle in order

to fit on the product.

- 2) The stiffness of the diaphragms is too low for preventing fibre wrinkling.

Computer simulation of the draping of a fabric over a hemisphere [ref.3] showed that the required shear angles are $\geq 30^\circ$

Figure 13: Computer simulation of the draping of a hemisphere.

5. CONCLUSIONS.

- The tensile strength of Glass/PEI increases with increasing processing temperature until 300 °C after which the strength remains constant.
- The inplane shear strength increases with increasing processing temperature until 300°C after which the strength remains constant.
- The optimum processing temperature for Glass/PEI from mechanical point of view is ≥ 300 °C.
- Diaphragm forming of hemispheres at 400 °C showed three phenomena: stripping of the matrix, Upilex wrinkles and fibre wrinkles.
- Stripping of the matrix can be solved by increasing the viscosity.
- Upilex wrinkling can be solved by increasing the viscosity.
- Fibre wrinkling can be solved by increasing the stiffness of the diaphragms.
- The optimum processing temperature for diaphragm forming of Glass/PEI is 300 °C.

REFERENCES

- 1 **Okine, R.K.** 'Analysis of forming parts from advanced thermoplastic sheet materials' *SAMPE J* (May/June 1989), pp 9-19.
- 2 **Bersee, H.E.N. and L.M.J. Robroek** 'The role of thermoplastic matrix in forming processes of composite materials' *Composites manufacturing Vol. 2 No. 3/4* 1992, pp 217-222.
- 3 **Bergsma, O.K.** 'Computer simulation of 3D forming processes of fabric reinforced plastics' *ICCM 9 Madrid* July 1993 .